

THE ROLE OF COOPERATION AND INTEGRATION IN THE EFFECTIVE MENEJMENT OF ORGANIZATIONS PRODUCING ORGANIC PRODUCTS

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Annotation: the article covers the urgent tasks of Management in organic agriculture, the development of cooperations and their socio-economic significance. Problems that arise in the process of organic vegetable production and methods for their effective management are analyzed.

Keywords: organic vegetable products, organic agriculture, cooperation, management efficiency, certification, strategic management.

Introduction: Organic vegetable farming is one of the important sectors of Agriculture, a direction that serves not only to protect the environment, but also to promote a healthy lifestyle. Despite the fact that Uzbekistan has the necessary natural resources for the production of organic vegetables, there are still many systemic shortcomings in this area. Including, the need to certify organic products, develop marketing strategies and establish scientifically based management processes remains relevant. The demand for organic products is increasing every year in the world market. Uzbekistan has very favorable natural conditions for the production of environmentally friendly products, and special attention to this area allows you to develop one of the most important sectors of the national economy. At the same time, organic vegetable growing has a great potential to meet the demand of the population for quality food, increase the volume of exports and ensure environmental sustainability. However, organic vegetable growing in Uzbekistan is not yet fully developed, and our country can expand its domestic and foreign markets in this area, leading the region in the production of environmentally friendly products. However, in the transition to organic agriculture, farms and farmers meet several obstacles. It will be very difficult for smallholders to compete in management and production, and it will be advisable for them to unite so that the population can lead a healthy lifestyle and create opportunities for themselves to receive high profits and provide new markets. Currently, organizations with a strong economy can be created in many enterprises, especially for peasant (farms), by organizing inter-farm cooperations and expanding them, reducing the path to achieving the goal. Such a solution to the problem makes it possible to harmonize the mutual assistance of organizations and provide effective management. Effective management, on the other hand, allows you to achieve a high final result. Cooperatives provide the following advantages for farmers:

- The possibility of using joint resources.
- Reduce marketing costs by working together in the sales process.
- Joint reduction of certification and maintenance costs.
- Lowering the cost of products through joint resource management.
- Increase household income and promote social stability.
- Increase the volume of products by opening new markets.

- Expanding access to loans and subsidies.
- Establishing joint marketing and advertising activities.
- Introduction of innovation by sharing technologies and knowledge.
- Increase the competitiveness of products.
- Formation of market prices that can withstand competition.
- Increase productivity through the use of agrotechnologies

Taking into account another characteristic of organic agriculture, it is possible to positively influence the final result of the activities of all sectors by integrating the activities of not only farmers' farms, but also separate specialized sectors involved in the storage, transportation, processing, and sale of this type of product until it reaches the consumer. Thus, the formation of the management system of organizations growing organic vegetable products at a new level of quality, the development of the entire process of growing and remanufacturing organic vegetables are now one of the most urgent tasks. Organic vegetable farming is one of the most labor-intensive and capital-intensive sectors of agriculture, as organic vegetable farming has a high proportion of manual labor in planting and harvesting vegetables, and its use of various management methods in human resource management is a concern. As an effective management practice, the ultimate goal of management is to ensure the profitability of the enterprise through the rational organization of the production process. The main goal of managing each organization is to achieve the highest level of profit at the cost of improving efficiency and ensuring the quality of products with minimal costs. At the same time, while it is possible to improve the standard of living by satisfying the population's demand for quality products, controlling financial indicators such as expenses, income and profit will help in making sound decisions.

Figure 1. Effective management of the process of growing organic vegetables .

To achieve the same results as above, it is necessary to carry out several tasks in the management of the process of growing and remanufacturing organic vegetable products:

1. Conducting market analysis and forecasting.
2. Making management decisions based on the data obtained.
3. Organization of production processes.
4. Setting up optimal human resource management options.
5. Organization of processes of certification of all stages of organic production and reproduction activities.
6. Marketing and advertising.
7. Monitoring the current state of decisions made in the management process.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it can be said that in fact, organic agriculture is a specific sector, which is significantly different from other sectors of the national economy. The role of Management in the development of this industry is very large, by establishing it correctly, it is possible to meet the demand of consumers for quality, international-standard food, and organizations have their place in the national and world markets, and improve the living standards of the population of our country. And opens up new prospects for the economy of Uzbekistan.

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